

The Need to Quickly Train Young Football Players in Tactical Actions

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Abstract:

This article describes the methodology of physical training of football players aged 17-19, based on the use of a series of microcycles in the training mesocycle with the predominant use of unidirectional loads.

Keywords: methodology, young football players, special performance, load orientation, block method.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, domestic coaches-practitioners have noted that the problem of adapting graduates of children's sports schools to the conditions of professional football is becoming more acute every year.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The state of training reserves in our country today is characterized by a discrepancy between its structure and the requirements of professional football. Firstly, there is no consistency in the education of highly qualified football players, and secondly, the training process is focused on the result in a particular match, and not on the preparation of competitive professionals¹. When working with this contingent, there is a clear imbalance between the volumes of educational and training and competitive activities. In leading schools, young men play 70-90 games per season. Such forcing the process of training young football players leads to the fact that about forty percent of graduates

¹ The art of training high-class football players // under. ed. N. M. Lyukshinova. - M.: 2013. - p. 135.

already have chronic diseases by the age of 16-17 and are not able to withstand the loads that are typical for today's professional players.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The defining feature of modern football is the high intensity of game activity, which places high demands on the athleticism, speed and endurance of modern qualified football players. Solving the problem of increasing the level of special physical performance of 17-19-year-old football players, we have developed a physical training technique based on the use of microcycles with predominantly unidirectional loads within individual mesocycles, which are combined into training blocks, in a one-year training cycle. Figure 1 shows the structure of the experimental methodology for the physical training of football players aged 17-19.

Fig. 1. The structure of the block method of physical training of football players 17-19 year old

The traditional construction of the annual training cycle of football players provides for three large phases: the accumulation of functional capabilities, their implementation and temporary loss (preparatory, competitive and transitional periods). When comparing the two approaches, large differences were revealed in the general physiological mechanism of adaptation: the traditional model mainly uses the effect of adaptation to parallel training loads, affecting many physical qualities, while the non-traditional model involves the imposition of "residual" training effects caused by concentrated unidirectional loads applied sequentially. In the context of preparing young players for the conditions of professional football, the block system used in the practice of sports seems to us more rational, since it will allow us to purposefully implement the planned tasks throughout the entire annual training cycle, reducing to a minimum the third "traditional" phase – deterioration of functionality².

CONCLUSION

Monitoring the dynamics of the level of special physical performance of football players provides for obtaining operational and current information to make adjustments to the stage and annual training plan. For this purpose, pedagogical testing is used, including determining the level of development of individual physical qualities, namely: general endurance (Cooper test); speed endurance (shuttle run 7x50 m); speed-strength qualities (30 m run, 60 m run, standing long jump). To assess the intensity of the load, it is supposed to determine the heart rate by the Polar running computer, and to regulate it, timing is required. To determine the volume of technical and tactical actions of football players in the game, the use of pedagogical observations is provided.

Thus, building the process of physical training of football players aged 17-19 by the block method will allow:

- purposefully develop the basic physical qualities of football players during a one-year training cycle;
- consistently increase the volume of loads of a pronounced predominant orientation when building each subsequent training block;
- optimally combine physical training and the process of improving the technical and tactical skills of young players.

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